

Manuscript Number: CLAY14123R1

Title: Photo-Oxidative Degradation of Injection Molded
Sepiolite/Polyamide66 Nanocomposites

Article Type: VSI:Euroclay2019

Section/Category:

Keywords: Polyamide66, Sepiolite, Clay/Polymer Nanocomposites, UV
exposure, Photo-oxidation

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Manuscript Region of Origin: SPAIN

Abstract: Every day clay/polymer nanocomposites are included in more industrial applications, due to its high performance. Because of this, nanocomposites may be submitted to extreme conditions of work, which could degrade it. Exposure to solar radiation in the presence of oxygen (photo-degradation) represents one of the major problems of the Clay/Polymer nanocomposites. In this study, samples of neat polyamide 66 (PA66-S-0) and reinforced nanocomposites with 1, 3, 5, 7 and 9 wt.% organophilized sepiolite (PA66-S-1, PA66-S-3, PA66-S-5, PA66-S-7 and PA66-S-9 samples) are analysed after UV exposure, following the standard accelerated degradation method UNE-EN-ISO 4892-2. The aim of this study is to establish the effect of UV exposure on the mechanical, optical and crystallographic properties of the new material. Tensile tests show a reduction in the ductility and an embrittlement after degradation process. In addition, an increase of transparency is confirmed with the UV exposure. The carbonyl index in the samples containing sepiolite is lower than in neat PA66 whereas the yellowness index is not affected by degradation. Sepiolite has an inhibitor effect on the formation of C=O bonds. These results indicate that breaking of chains of PA66 starts in the amorphous region and that it is lower in the nanocomposites due to the low diffusion of oxygen induced by the sepiolite. This affirmation is corroborated by the obtained diffraction patterns.

1 **Photo-Oxidative Degradation of Injection Molded**
2 **Sepiolite/Polyamide66 Nanocomposites**

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18 **Abstract**

19 Every day clay/polymer nanocomposites are included in more industrial
20 applications, due to its high performance. Because of this, nanocomposites may be
21 submitted to extreme conditions of work, which could degrade it. Exposure to solar
22 radiation in the presence of oxygen (photo-degradation) represents one of the major

23 problems of the Clay/Polymer nanocomposites. In this study, samples of neat polyamide
24 66 (PA66-S-0) and reinforced nanocomposites with 1, 3, 5, 7 and 9 wt.%
25 organophilized sepiolite (PA66-S-1, PA66-S-3, PA66-S-5, PA66-S-7 and PA66-S-9
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29 new material. Tensile tests show a reduction in the ductility and an embrittlement after
30 degradation process. In addition, an increase of transparency is confirmed with the UV
31 exposure. The carbonyl index in the samples containing sepiolite is lower than in neat
32 PA66 whereas the yellowness index is not affected by degradation. Sepiolite has an
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39 **1. Introduction**

40 The number of applications that require advanced materials capable of
41 withstanding the work conditions to which they are subjected is increasing daily. Much
42 research in materials science and engineering therefore focuses on finding new
43 advanced materials (Okada and Usuki, 2006; Kotal and Bhowmick, 2015; Valino et al.,
44 2019). Improving the mechanical properties of clay/polymer nanocomposites (CPN)
45 makes them ideal for many applications (Butnaru et al., 2016; Fernández-Barranco et al.,

46 2014; Mukhopadhyay et al., 2020; Pfaendner, 2010; Sharma et al., 2019), and they are
47 now expanding to numerous outdoor applications. Their usefulness depends, however,
48 on their durability in a particular environment, or their interaction with environmental
49 factors. The versatility of these advanced materials makes it possible that they will be
50 exposed to UV radiation which, in the presence of atmospheric oxygen, causes them to
51 degrade, affecting their properties through photo-oxidative degradation, one of the
52 primary sources of damage to polymers in outdoor applications (Bocchini et al., 2010;
53 Bussière et al, 2013; Olewnik-Kruszkowska, 2015; Pandey et al, 2005; Remili et al.,
54 2009; Zaidi et al., 2010). Studying the degradation and stability of these materials is
55 thus an issue of great interest from the scientific and industrial point of view, since
56 better knowledge of the degradation mechanisms will enable greater time of service for
57 these products.

58 Polyamide 66 (PA66) is a thermoplastic polymer widely used as matrix in CPN
59 due to its excellent mechanical and thermal resistance, good barrier properties and
60 recyclability (Okada and Usuki, 2006 and references therein). Photo-oxidation of PA66
61 occurs through a complex mechanism of chain breakage (Carroccio and Puglisi, 2004;
62 Margolin et al., 1976; Thanki and Singh, 1998), which begins in the carbon atom
63 adjacent to the amide group when a proton (H) is lost through the action of incident
64 photons. This process generates a highly reactive free radical, which reacts by forming
65 different intermediate groups (aldehyde, alkyl, carboxyl and hydroperoxide) to form
66 degradation products that may or may not contain the intermediates, depending on the
67 mechanism by which the reaction occurred. PA66 shows two mechanisms of photo-
68 dissociation, termed Norrish I and Norrish II (Carroccio and Puglisi, 2004 and
69 references therein). Both the intermediate and the final degradation products are highly
70 reactive and non-accumulative, making it very difficult to predict the photo-dissociation

71 mechanism. PA66 is semi-crystalline; amorphous and crystalline zones coexist in its
72 structure. Due to its low permeability and high diffusion of O₂, the amorphous zone is
73 the zone most susceptible to photo-oxidation (Cerruti et al., 2005; Thanki and Singh,
74 1998), and the crystalline zone is affected superficially in shorter chains when most of
75 the amorphous zone has disappeared. Furthermore, photo-dissociation can cause some
76 amorphous chains to crystallize, making the material more fragile (Thanki et al., 2001).

77 Regarding photo-oxidative degradation of CPN, some studies performed on
78 polymers reinforced with montmorillonite (Mt) (Qin et al., 2004; Qin et al, 2005), it has
79 generally been observed that the clay nanoparticles accelerate the mechanism of CPN
80 degradation. Acceleration occurs because the remains of organic ammonium used in the
81 organophilization process of Mt can create initiation routes (active positions) for
82 degradation where the Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ from the Mt act as a catalyst (Bussière et al., 2013).
83 These effects are less severe when the clay used as reinforcing agent is a fibrous clay
84 (Bocchini et al., 2010). The fibrous habit of sepiolite (Sep) produces a network in the
85 polymer matrix that is less penetrable to oxygen, preventing the oxygen to react with the
86 polymer chains. In some cases, the Sep prevents the polymer from crystallizing with
87 photo-oxidation by causing immobility in the chains. In fact Sep has been used as a
88 stabilizing agent against photo-oxidation in other systems (Casal et al., 2001).

89 The aim of this work is to analyse how photo-oxidation affects the
90 crystallographic, mechanical, and optical properties of CPN Sep/PA66, taking into
91 account the degree of degradation caused through a standard accelerated degradation
92 method (UNE-EN-ISO 4892-2). For that purpose, a set of samples containing different
93 Sep percentage has been used: 0, 1, 3, 5, 7 and 9 wt.% (samples PA66-S-0, PA66-S-1,
94 PA66-S-3, PA66-S-5, PA66-S-7 and PA66-S-9, respectively). Prior studies have proved

95 the increasing of mechanical properties related to the individual phases and the good
96 dispersion of the Sep in the polymer matrix (Fernández-Barranco et al., 2015).

97 **2. Materials and Methods**

98 The CPN studied in this work was manufactured with PA66 (Dinalon®, Grupo
99 Repol, Spain) and organophilized sepiolite with a protonated quaternary ammonium salt
100 (Tolsa S.A., Spain). The PA66 granulates and organosepiolite were previously dried in
101 a vacuum oven during 24 h at 80°C. Pellets were manufactured via melt intercalation
102 using a double screw extruder (250 rpm, 250 °C), following the process described in a
103 previous work (Yebra-Rodríguez et al., 2009).

104 The PA66 matrix was reinforced with different clay loading: 1, 3, 5, 7 and 9 wt.%, and
105 the obtained samples were designated as PA66-S-1, PA66-S-3, PA66-S-5, PA66-S-7
106 and PA66-S-9, respectively. Neat PA66 was manufactured following the same
107 procedure (sample PA66-S-0) to guarantee identical preparation conditions. The pellets
108 of the samples were injected in an injection molding machine (BABYPLAST 6/10,
109 CRONOPLAST) under the following conditions: tool pressure 25 MPa, cylinder
110 temperature 285 C and tool temperature 50 °C. Two different injection molds were
111 used: plate with 1 mm thickness (80 x 50 mm), and a specific mold according to the
112 UNE-EN ISO 527-2 standard procedure. After injection, the CPN samples were
113 exposed to radiation following the method described in the UNE-EN-ISO 4892-2
114 standard. A test chamber (SOLARBOX 1500e RH, COFOMEGRA) was used, with
115 wide band of 300-400 nm and narrow-band of 340 nm. The cycle type was the number
116 2 from the method A, with constant irradiation (from a xenon arc) of 550 W/m² and 65
117 ± 3°C controlled by a Black Standard Thermometer (BST), without night. The relative
118 humidity was controlled and monitored. An ultrasonic humidifier ensures reliable

119 functioning for long time. The total exposure time was 240 h; every 2 h the samples
120 were immersed in deionizer water during 18 min. The resulting samples were
121 designated as PA66-S-0_UV, PA66-S-1_UV, PA66-S-3_UV, PA66-S-5_UV, PA66-S-
122 7_UV and PA66-S-9_UV.

123 Mechanical properties were determined using an Universal Testing Machine
124 MTS InsightTM with 5 kN load capacity, equipped with an extensometer and following
125 the method described in UNE-EN ISO 527-1. Transparency was calculated with a non-
126 contact SpectraScan PR-704 spectroradiometer (Photo Research, Chatsworth, USA)
127 using the CIELAB method (Guinea et al., 2010). The degradation was quantified by the
128 Carbonyl Index (CI) and Yellowness Index (YI). The infrared spectroscopic analyses
129 (FT-IR) were used to obtain the Carbonyl Index. The samples were analysed in a FT-IR
130 Bruker Tensor 27 spectrometer in the attenuated total reflection mode (ATR) between
131 400 and 4000 cm⁻¹ at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. The CI was calculated from the spectra
132 comparing the integrated area in the carbonyl region (1710 - 1760 cm⁻¹) with the CH₂
133 scissor bond region (1458 – 1468 cm⁻¹), which is unaffected by the degradation. The CI
134 is defined as the ratio of the integrated carbonyl band and the reference band (Dong and
135 Gijsman, 2010).

136 The ASTM provides a standard practice for calculating a yellowness index YI
137 from instrumentally color coordinates (ASTM 313-96). This YI is as follows

$$138 \quad YI = \frac{100(C_X X - C_Z Z)}{Y} \quad (1)$$

139 where X, Y and Z are the tristimulus values of the sample and C_X and C_Z are
140 coefficients depending on the experimental conditions. With the illuminant/observer
141 combination used in this experiment (D65/10°), values given by the ASTM for C_X and
142 C_Z are 1.3013 and 1.1489, respectively. CIE tristimulus values X, Y and Z are the basic

143 values used to specify a color, and can be transformed to other colorimetric coordinates
144 of other color systems. The International Commission on Illumination CIE (CIE, 1970,
145 1986, 2004) defined the tristimulus values as

$$146 \quad V = \int_a^b W_V(\lambda)R(\lambda)d\lambda \quad (2)$$

147 with $V = X, Y$ and Z , where

$$148 \quad W_X(\lambda) = \kappa S(\lambda)x(\lambda) \quad (3), \quad W_Y(\lambda) = \kappa S(\lambda)y(\lambda) \quad (4), \quad W_Z(\lambda) = \kappa S(\lambda)z(\lambda) \quad (5)$$

149 and where $S(\lambda)$ is the relative spectral power distribution of the illuminant (in our case,
150 illuminant D65), $x(\lambda)$, $y(\lambda)$, and $z(\lambda)$ are the CIE standard observer color-matching
151 functions (here, standard observer CIE1964 10°), $R(\lambda)$ is the spectral reflectance factor
152 of the object color considered, (a-b) is the visible range of wavelengths (380-780 nm),
153 and κ is a normalizing factor defined as follows

$$154 \quad \kappa = 100 / \int_a^b S(\lambda)y(\lambda)d\lambda \quad (6)$$

155 These values X , Y and Z were obtained with a non-contact SpectraScan PR-704
156 spectroradiometer (Photo Research, Chatsworth, USA) with a 4% measurement
157 accuracy and standard deviation of repeat measurements over a 15-minute period less
158 than 0.1 % (Perez et al., 2000) following the method as described elsewhere (Yebra-
159 Rodríguez et al., 2014).

160 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was carried out in an equipment DSC
161 822e, Mettler Toledo. The samples were heated over the temperature range of 25-300
162 °C with a heating rate of 5 °C/min and under nitrogen flow (50mL/min) for avoiding
163 extra degradation. Crystallinity Index (W_c) was calculated from the ratio between the
164 enthalpy of melting (ΔH_m), obtained for each sample from the area in the DSC curve

165 between onset and endset temperatures) and that of a fully crystalline PA66 sample (196
166 J/g, Lee and Phillips, 2007), according to the following formula, where w_{PA66} is the
167 weight fraction of PA66:

$$W_c(\%) = \frac{\Delta H_m}{196 \text{ J/g}} \cdot \frac{100}{w_{PA66}} \quad (7)$$

168 Diffraction patterns of the samples before and after photo-oxidative degradation
169 were obtained with a X-ray Empyrean diffractometer with the PIXcel-3D detector
170 (PANalytical, The Netherlands). The radiation was CuK_α (1.54178 Å) and the
171 parameters: 40 kV and 35 mA. The range of the Bragg angle was between $2\theta = 3 - 35^\circ$.

172 3. Results and discussion

173 The effects of the ultraviolet light and environmental oxygen on the samples
174 after degradation are shown in Fig.1. In general, the values for yield stress (σ_m , Fig.
175 1A), Young's Modulus (E, Fig. 1B), and strain at break (ϵ_B , Fig. 1C) are lower in the
176 degraded samples, indicating that the material generally loses mechanical properties due
177 to degradation (Bussière et al., 2013; Dintcheva et al., 2010). The value of σ_m (Fig. 1A)
178 is the least influenced by degradation, indicating that degraded CPN have similar tensile
179 strength before and after degradation. In contrast, E decreases considerably during
180 aging, a decrease greater than 1 GPa in all cases (Fig. 1B). The greatest loss of E occurs
181 in the sample PA66-S-9_UV, which experiences a nearly 70% loss of stiffness.
182 Reduction in elongation at break is common for all polymers after UV exposure, thus E
183 is used for monitoring the aging of polymers (Torikai et al., 1990). The value of ϵ_B (Fig.
184 1C) is the value most influenced by UV exposure, and it decreases drastically after
185 exposure. Even in CPN with little reinforcement (PA66-S-1_UV), loss of ϵ_B is greater
186 than 81%. In the other CPN samples, the value of ϵ_B decreases more with higher

187 percentages of sepiolite, the most fragile sample being PA66-S-9_UV. This result
188 indicates that the nanocomposites embrittle with photo-oxidation without a drastic
189 decrease in tensile strength (Thanki et al., 2001). These results are associated with two
190 processes that compete as a consequence of UV exposure: chain scission and chain
191 crosslinking. Chain scission decreases the molecular weight and yield stress of
192 polymers, whereas chain crosslinking increases yield stress and embrittles polymers. As
193 a result of these processes the changes in yield stress are negligible.

194 The transparency values of the CPN samples before and after UV exposure (Fig.
195 2) show that the degraded samples display higher values than the undegraded samples,
196 being PA66-S-0_UV the most influenced sample after the photo-oxidative degradation
197 process. The tendency to increase in opacity as the percentage of sepiolite reinforcement
198 increases continues in the degraded samples, as the sepiolite renders specimen more
199 opaque. The changes in the mechanical and optical qualities of the CPN are due to their
200 structural modification, since exposure to light sources in the presence of O₂ affects the
201 polymer chains (Carroccio et al., 2003; Cerruti et al., 2005). The photons from the
202 ultraviolet radiation influence the polymer chains, breaking them and giving rise to new
203 C=O bonds and thus carbonyl groups, when the process of photo-dissociation occurs.

204 The indexes CI and YI (Figs. 3 and 4, respectively) were calculated to measure
205 the degree of degradation (through the extension of the C=O bonds) in the samples after
206 the photo-oxidation process. Fig. 3 compares the values of CI obtained for the samples
207 before and after degradation. The undegraded samples do not show a value of 0 for CI,
208 since the PA66 structure contains amide groups with C=O bonds detectable through FT-
209 IR. Furthermore, these bonds form with the breaking of the chains that occurs in the
210 extrusion and injection processes needed to obtain the CPN (Thanki, 1998). The value
211 of CI in the samples before degradation is lower than those in the degraded samples.

212 The highest value of CI corresponds to the sample PA66-S-0_UV. The aged
213 nanocomposites have a value close to that obtained in the undegraded samples and less
214 than that of the degraded sample without sepiolite (PA66-S-0_UV sample). Since the
215 degradation can occur by different mechanisms, Norrish I and Norrish II (Carroccio and
216 Puglisi, 2004), and may or may not be complete, the sepiolite prevents the
217 decomposition through a similar mechanism by which it occurs in neat PA66, a
218 mechanism that does not encourage the formation of C=O groups. In general, the
219 predominant decomposition mechanism of PA66 is Norrish I. This mechanism produces
220 a greater number of decomposition products (intermediate and/or final) with C=O bonds
221 in their formula. In contrast, the data obtained indicate that the presence of sepiolite
222 favours Norrish II, in which the products of decomposition have fewer C=O groups.
223 This mechanism is favoured by the structural organization of both phases in the
224 Clay/Polymer Nanocomposite and the good dispersion of the sepiolite in the polymer
225 matrix (Fernández-Barranco et al., 2016), which impedes the passage of O₂ and thus the
226 formation of C=O groups that would increase the CI. Thus, the sepiolite has an
227 inhibiting effect on the formation of C=O in the photo-oxidative degradation of the
228 polymer, as it also occurs in other oxidative degradation processes (Yebra-Rodriguez et
229 al., 2014). CPN samples with a value lower than 5 wt.% sepiolite show a CI value
230 closer to that of the undegraded samples (PA66-S-1_UV and PA66-S-3_UV), whereas
231 PA66-S-5_UV, PA66-S-7_UV, and PA66-S-9_UV (Fig. 4.5-3) show a tendency toward
232 increase in the CI. As the percentage of reinforcement increases (> 5 wt.%), the CI
233 increases, moving farther from the CI value in the undegraded samples. This increase in
234 degraded nanocomposite samples is always lower than that obtained for sample PA66-
235 S-0_UV.

236 The results of the YI obtained for the samples before and after UV exposure are
237 shown in Fig.4. The YI values are similar in samples with similar content of sepiolite
238 before and after photo-oxidative aging. The YI increases when the sepiolite content in
239 the matrix increases but, in contrast to the other degradation processes, is not influenced
240 by ultraviolet radiation (Yebra-Rodriguez et al., 2014). This occurs because exposure to
241 ultraviolet light in the presence of oxygen does not cause degradation products such as
242 pyrrole to form in the polymer and carbonaceous silicates in the case of the sepiolite,
243 such that the yellowness of the nanocomposites does not change (Levchik et al., 1999).

244 Table 1 displays the calculated crystallinity index and melting temperature (T_m)
245 of the studied samples. The crystallinity index (W_c) depends on the quantity of sepiolite
246 and has an oscillating tendency which is also observed in the degraded CPN. W_c varies
247 in a similar way when the Clay/Polymer Nanocomposite is degraded, such that photo-
248 oxidation does not produce a relevant change in W_c . Some studies show that photo-
249 oxidative degradation of polymers begins in the amorphous zone, as O_2 penetrates more
250 easily there (Cerruti et al., 2005; Thanki et al., 2001). In this case, the effect is reflected
251 in the values of melting temperature before and after degradation. The values of T_m
252 increase slightly or remains the same in all degraded samples, and less in the sample
253 PA66-S-9_UV, in relation to the undegraded samples. This phenomenon contrasts with
254 what occurs in other PA66 systems, where degradation does affect the crystalline zone
255 (Cerruti et al., 2005; Cerruti and Carfagna, 2010). This increase involves a reduction in
256 the amorphous zones, which are generally melted more easily than the crystalline zones.
257 Further, these results show signs of recrystallization in the amorphous zone, which
258 contributes to the embrittlement of the CPN, hence the loss of mechanical properties (E
259 and ϵ_B), which indicate loss of ductibility (Figs. 1B and 1C).

260 The loss of amorphous zones in the PA66 is also reflected in the diffraction
261 patterns of the CPN (Fig. 5). The zone of the diffraction pattern between 5-12 °2θ
262 displays a shoulder that spans the whole range, typically corresponding to the
263 amorphous region in the polymer structure. This shoulder disappears in the degraded
264 samples, confirming the partial collapse of the amorphous zone already observed after
265 DSC analyses (T_m , Table 1). The Bragg angle of the diffraction peaks of the PA66 α
266 structure (20.3 °2θ and 23.2 °2θ, corresponding to the planes (100) and (010)/(110),
267 respectively) (Bunn and Garner, 1947) are not affected by degradation, since the
268 spacing between adjacent planes remains unchanged by either the action of the sepiolite
269 rods (which are placed perpendicular to the PA66 lamellae through hydrogen bonds
270 without modifying the PA66 chains) or the degradation. However, the loss of
271 amorphous region provokes an increase in the intensity of PA66 diffraction peaks in the
272 degraded samples with low sepiolite content (PA66-S-0_UV, PA66-S-1_UV, and
273 PA66-S-3_UV). Photo-oxidation promotes the recrystallization of the PA66, according
274 to the results obtained in the transparency test (Fig. 2). The characteristic peaks of the
275 CPN structure (Fernández-Barranco et al., 2018), which appear at 8.70 °2θ, 17.55 °2θ,
276 26.03 °2θ and 32.86 °2θ in the nanocomposites containing 5 wt.% of sepiolite and
277 above, remain after degradation of the samples and sharpen in the diffractions patterns
278 of the nanocomposite containing the highest percentage of sepiolite (PA66-S-9_UV
279 sample, Fig. 5D). The degradation of the amorphous region in these samples promotes
280 the ordering of the CPN structure, in which the sepiolite fibers place between adjacent
281 PA66 adjacent lamellae and trigger higher order degree in the CPN suprastructure.
282 However, the crystallinity index (Table 1) shows that, despite increasing the ordering of
283 the structure, the crystallite size of the polymer is necessarily smaller. Moreover,
284 according to the tensile tests (linked to the crystallinity of the sample), the more

285 crystalline a material, the greater its resistance, which fits the results shown in Fig. 1A.
286 The loss of amorphous zones (more ductile) and recrystallization of PA66 causes the
287 embrittlement of the CPN, as shown in Fig. 1C.

288 **4. Conclusions**

289 The behaviour of nanocomposites Sep/PA66 was evaluated after photo-oxidative
290 exposure. Mechanical properties and transparency of the Clay/Polymer Nanocomposites
291 are clearly affected. A high reduction of ductility, resulting in an embrittlement, has
292 been observed. After UV exposure, samples are more translucent and therefore more
293 crystalline when the percentage of Sep increases in the CPN. Carbonyl indices of
294 nanocomposite samples are lower than those of neat PA66, which indicates that
295 sepiolite nanofibers prevent the formation of carboxyl bonds. DSC and XRD analyses
296 demonstrate that the ageing of nanocomposites starts in the amorphous zone of PA66,
297 thus the Clay/Polymer nanocomposites present higher crystallinity degree after UV
298 exposure (i.e. the amount of crystals increases), although the crystals are not more
299 perfect. The more crystalline and the greater resistance of the new material is in
300 concordance with the mechanical analyses. Loss of amorphous (more ductile) zones and
301 crystallization of some chains cause the CPN to embrittle considerably. The
302 crosslinking structure formed between Sep and PA66 impedes the diffusion of oxygen
303 in the hybrid, which acts as a catalyser in the UV degradation. That is, sepiolite has an
304 inhibitory effect in the photo-oxidative degradation of Clay/Polymer nanocomposites.

305

306 **Acknowledgments**

307 This research was supported by Centro de Estudios Avanzados en Ciencias de la Tierra
308 (University of Jaén, Spain), Andalusian Research Groups RNM-325, TEP-138 (CICE,

309 JA, Spain). The authors thank CICT (University of Jaén, Spain), CIC (University of
310 Granada, Spain), and the technicians for data collection.

311

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411

412 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

413 **Fig. 1.** Mechanical properties of the CPN samples before and after photo-oxidative
414 degradation. A) Yield Stress, B) Young's Modulus C) Strain at Break.

415 **Fig. 02.** Transparency data of the studied samples before and after photo-oxidative
416 degradation. Less than ± 0.1 error.

417 **Fig. 3.** Carbonyl Index with standard deviation before and after photo-oxidative
418 degradation.

419 **Fig. 4.** Yellowness Index of the CPN samples before and after photo-oxidative
420 degradation. Less than ± 0.01 error.

421 **Fig.5.** Diffraction patterns of Sep and neat PA66 (A) and the samples with 1 (B), 5 (C)
422 and 9 (D) wt.% of sepiolite loading, before and after photo-oxidative degradation.

423

Sample	PA66-S-0	PA66-S-1	PA66-S-3	PA66-S-5	PA66-S-7	PA66-S-9
A	0					
B		1				
C			3			
D				5		
E					7	
F						9

- The influence of the sepiolite on the behavior of the nanocomposites after UV exposure has been studied.
- Sepiolite has an inhibitor effect on the formation of C=O.
- The crystallographic arrangement of PA66 and sepiolite hinders the oxygen diffusion.
- The breaking of chains is lower in nanocomposites due of the sepiolite.

Table 1. Thermal data and crystallinity index from DSC of the samples before and after photo-oxidative degradation. Less than ± 0.1 error.

Sample	W_c (%)	T_{onset} (°C)	T_m (°C)	T_{endset} (°C)
PA66-S-0	37.2	257.2	265.2	269.0
PA66-S-1	34.0	256.2	264.8	269.1
PA66-S-3	34.3	254.9	264.9	270.7
PA66-S-5	35.0	256.2	264.1	269.3
PA66-S-7	33.7	255.1	264.3	270.5
PA66-S-9	30.9	252.5	264.0	268.7
PA66-S-0_UV	35.5	256.6	266.4	271.3
PA66-S-1_UV	36.0	259.7	266.7	269.5
PA66-S-3_UV	32.6	254.3	264.9	269.2
PA66-S-5_UV	33.3	253.3	264.6	268.4
PA66-S-7_UV	32.6	257.4	265.0	269.0
PA66-S-9_UV	32.3	250.3	263.6	268.1

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

M. Dolores La Rubia

C. Fernández-Barranco: Investigation, writing the original draft preparation. F. J. Navas-Martos: Validation, formal analysis. A. Yebra: Optical investigation. A. Yebra-Rodríguez and M. Dolores La Rubia: Conceptulization, methodology, Writing-Reviewing and Editing. J. Jiménez-Millán and A. E. Koziol Supervision: